

RoguePlots_CBI-24-TE: This pdf contains the RoguePlots created for the 24 fossils resulted from the constrained Bayesian Inference analysis for 24 fossils using total evidence data (CBI-24-TE)

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X_Archaeanthus_linnenbergeri

PP

X_Archaestella_verticillatus

PP

X_Bertilanthus_scanicus

PP

X_Canrightia_resinifera

PP

X_Carpestella_lacunata

PP

X_Cecilanthus_polymerus

PP

X_Chloranthistemon_endressii

PP

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PP

X_Divisestylus_brevistamineus

PP

X_Florissantia_quilchenensis

PP

X_Kajanthus_lusitanicus

PP

X_Mabelia_connatifila

PP

X_Mauldinia_mirabilis

PP

X_Microvictoria_svitkoana

PP

X_Paleocclusia_chevalieri

PP

X_Paradinandra_suecica

PP

X_Pentapetalum_trifasciculandricus

PP

X_Platydiscus_peltatus

PP

X_Quadriplatanus_georgianus

PP

X_Rariglanda_jerseyensis

PP

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